

Social Media and Empowerment of Rural Women: A Sociological Analysis

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Abstract

As a powerful tool of digital media, social media has contributed to the expansion of the global communication network. During the on-going pandemic the significance of those digital venues has doubled. Social policy and social media have grown highly reticulate in recent years. Women now have a place on social media to communicate their issues, beliefs and viewpoints through blogs, online campaigns, discussion boards, chats and more. Social media has demonstrated the power to increase awareness of and accountability for women's rights while combating prejudice and stereotypes. In addition to inspiring action on the streets of cities worldwide and pushing policy makers to increase their commitments to gender equality, it has proven to be a potent tool for raising awareness of women's rights problems. People are increasingly using social media platforms to express themselves, communicate, and advocate for social change. By providing information access, building networks, and amplifying marginalized voices, these platforms have the potential to empower women. This study explores the connection between women's empowerment and social media use, as well as how these platforms either help or hinder the advancement of women's rights, independence, and leadership. Increased use of social media and mobile devices is one of the state's good trends among rural women. This study aims to understand why rural women choose to use or refrain from utilizing social media. The main method of gathering data was conducting 100 semi-structured individual interviews in one of the villages in Rudrapur, Udham Singh Nagar (U.K.). The method of sampling is purposive. The examination of data indicates that women in rural areas have engaged with social media. The majority of them utilize Facebook, Whatsapp and YouTube for interacting, acquiring new skills, exploring recipes and viewing the latest fashion trends. Women who engaged with social media felt it positively influenced their status and contributed to their self-empowerment.

Keywords

Women empowerment, Literacy, Quality of life, Social media, Social policy, Digital activisms

Introduction

"A woman is the full circle. Within her is the power to create, nurture and transform." — Diane Mariechild

In today's world, social media has become indispensable, causing revolutionary change in every sphere of society. People can share information on social media both domestically and abroad, and it has become a habit and a necessity. God created males and females, and women are the ones who procreate (Sexena, R. 2010). Social Media has emerged as a force for social change that has aided and encouraged women's empowerment in a number of ways, including drawing attention to women's rights and combating prejudice and stereotypes worldwide. Through blogs, chats, online campaigns, online discussion forums, and online communities, social media has provided a forum for discussing issues and challenges facing women that are typically not shared or propagated by mainstream media. Nearly every individual in society is currently familiar with the use of social media in their daily lives, whether for entertainment or other purposes. The variety of social media platforms has been integrated to function as a primary tool for maintaining connections with friends and family, providing access to news and information, facilitating the sharing of personal updates, and engaging with businesses and communities. Social media encompasses online platforms and applications that enable users to connect, share information, ideas, and content with one another through various forms of communication, such as text, photos, videos, and more. People can virtually interact and engage with each other through platforms like Facebook, YouTube, Vlogs, Instagram, Twitter, WhatsApp, LinkedIn, Snapchat, and others. Every social media user can obtain any type of authentic knowledge and information from a surprising Google search page. Social media has been shown to be influential in empowering women across all aspects of their lives, including population control, promoting

literacy, and enhancing quality of life. The majority of women in rural areas are rapidly switching from electronic media, such as watching television and listening to the radio, to social media across all age groups. Since women are increasingly using social media, it has a significant impact on them. While social media is widely acknowledged to have an impact on people's lifestyles and that it is constantly being used to determine the exact nature of these influences in every society and nation, particularly on women, this craze for social media has raised a number of questions about its effects on society (Routray S. 2011). Women interact and converse with their peer groups on a daily basis using a variety of media platforms including social media. Social media, which is primarily used to disseminate information, is crucial for women, including female students. Social media's growing popularity has expanded knowledge and made information sharing and transfer easier. Women can now post inspirational ideas and share information on social media with ease. Women's use of social media has become ingrained in their daily lives, with private activities being shared publicly (Satpathi 2011). There are close relationships between society and media. These days, it's easy to see how much the media has affected society. Our society's structure and functioning are reflected in the media. As technology has advanced, our society has also seen an expansion in people's ideas and thoughts. Every single invention, from the printing press to the newest smartphones, has been embraced by our society. In the past, people would use prints and sketches to communicate, but as time went on, communication methods improved (Pandey and Singh 2017). In every aspect of life, it plays a vital role in raising people's awareness. The fourth estate of democracy is thought to be the media. In many forms, including radio, television, books, magazines, newspapers, the internet, and more, it has become an essential part of our lives. (Gupta, 2018).

Area of The Study

Area of the study was Bhoora Rani Village in Rudrapur block of Udham Singh Nagar district (U.K.). Uttarakhand district of Udham Singh Nagar contains the Rudrapur block. Rudrapur community development block of Udham Singh Nagar consists of 88 villages in total. In which, according to the data from the 2011 Census, Bhoora Rani Village has a total population of 7224 consisting of 1538 families residing in the village. The male population in Bhoora Rani Village is 3849, while the female population is 3375.

Objective of study

The aim of this research paper is to assess the impact of social media on empowerment of rural women in Bhoora Rani Village in Rudrapur block of Udham Singh Nagar district (U.K.)

Review of Literature

The media is a medium for expressing other people's opinions. The majority of women's leisure activities include watching television, listening to radio shows that interest them, reading newspapers for information, or reading books or journals to kill time. An excellent source of informal education is the media. By raising awareness of their issues, determining the causes of them, and offering solutions, media writers can assist people. The majority of issues that women and their families face can be resolved through women's empowerment. By raising awareness of their rights and responsibilities in society, it may be the greatest way to advance education and the capacity for independent thought. The media can be very helpful in educating people about ways to empower women and accept their role in the social advancement of society (Akhter and Naheed 2014). In his 2017 article, "Media's Role in the Women Empowerment of India" G. Padmaja examines how empowering women contributes to the general growth of women's lives and how the media aids in dispelling sexism and stereotypes.

Brindha D, Jayaseelan R, Kadeswaran S, (2020) explored the complex relationship that exists between women and social media in India. In India, where gender disparities exist in internet access, this study examines the influence of social media on women's empowerment. Social media presents both opportunities and challenges as a tool for gender equality and societal change, as the study reveals by examining women's perspectives and experiences in the digital sphere.

Kumari (2020) stated that social media is a crucial forum for discussing women's rights and advised policymakers and the government to create promises and policies for gender equality. Singh, S. (2018) in his article titled "Empower the Rural Women to Empower the Community" states that numerous government initiatives exist to assist and guide rural women through various entitlements, which have also facilitated their unification into Self Help Groups (SHGs). Initiatives such as the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana support over 50 million small business proprietors, with a significant proportion (78 percent) being women. These SHGs, comprised of enterprising women, enable the community as a whole to investigate business opportunities, secure access to resources (human, intellectual, and financial) necessary to initiate their enterprises, and seek avenues for further expansion. The Mahila Shakti Kendra is another initiative designed to empower rural women by providing opportunities for skill enhancement, employment, digital literacy, health, and nutrition. Dixit (2020) emphasized that social media

plays a significant role in influencing changes in individuals' social life status, mental well-being, self-concept, self-esteem, decision-making, and technology usage.

The preceding discussion has shown that social media platforms serve as instruments for women's empowerment, enhancing the primary indicators of empowerment. Indicators of women's empowerment, including literacy among women, access to information, opportunities for self-decision making, updates in technology, group communications, and the demonstration of various economic activities, are positively impacted by social media platforms. Today, social media plays a crucial role in our daily lives. Social media has a major impact on rural women's overall development, according to earlier research conducted in many states and nations. In this context, the researcher wants to know the answer to the following query in this situation. "How rural women in Bhoora Rani Village in Rudrapur block, Udham Singh Nagar, U.K. were empowered by social media."

Main Text

Women Empowerment

The empowerment of women is a crucial concept that emphasizes the active and meaningful involvement of women in society. Empowered women possess the capability to fully participate in social, economic, and political spheres, thus contributing to societal progress (Vardhan, 2017). Women who attain empowerment place a high value on financial independence and endeavor to escape cycles of dependency. This mindset not only alters their lifestyles but also allows them to have a say in decision-making processes, both personally and professionally (Rehman, 2013). Women can achieve empowerment through intentional activities, equity-focused strategies, and systematically organized approaches that ensure they have an equal role in networks, workplaces, and markets. To enhance the current levels of women's empowerment across various societies, numerous tiered efforts are being implemented globally. Traditional mass media have proven to be effective and influential tools in supporting women's empowerment initiatives. Nevertheless, in today's world, social media has emerged as a highly powerful and effective medium that not only raises awareness about women's issues in the public sphere but also encourages discussions and exploration of diverse solutions (Freiri, 1973). As social media provides women with more avenues to express themselves and seek solutions to their challenges, current efforts to empower women are increasingly focusing on it rather than on traditional methods (Morahan-Martin, 2000).

Empowering women involves unlocking their potential and providing them with the necessary resources to take control of their lives. As noted by Schuler (1986) this process includes assisting women in enhancing their existing skills and abilities, enabling them to actively participate in the decision-making processes that affect their well-being. Moser (1993) further indicates that the initiatives of feminist activists in developing countries form the basis of this empowerment journey, with the ultimate aim of transferring power to women. By supporting women in this manner, we can foster a more equitable and inclusive society where every individual has a voice. Empowerment represents a journey that commences when individuals assume control of their lives and make decisions independently, without seeking the approval of others. According to Sen and Batliwala (2000), this self-determination process signifies the beginning of a new phase, where individuals are no longer reliant on others to meet their needs. Additionally, Sen and Grown (1987) noted that women's empowerment is frequently marked by their heightened involvement in economic and political spheres, which provides them with greater authority over their lives.

Different forms of women empowerment encouraged by social media:

Makamba website states that there are six elements that make up women's empowerment:

Cognitive Empowerment:

"Women understand of their conditions of subordination and the reasons of such conditions at both micro and macro levels of society" is one aspect of cognitive empowerment. It entails both dispelling outdated notions that underpin potent gender ideas and gaining fresh knowledge to develop an alternative understanding of gender interactions.

Psychological Empowerment:

Developing emotions that women can use to better their circumstances is a component of psychological empowerment. This entails developing the conviction that they can be successful in their attempts at transformation.

Economic Empowerment:

In order for women to be considered economically empowered, they must be able to participate in productive activities that grant them a certain amount of autonomy, however limited and initially challenging.

Political Empowerment:

Organizing and mobilizing for change and democracy is a component of political empowerment. Therefore, in addition to individual awareness, an empowerment process needs to include community awareness and action. In order to achieve social change, the idea of collaborative action is essential.

Social Empowerment:

The “process to modify the allocation of power in interpersonal relations among diverse people, cultures and activities of the society” is known as social empowerment. In the past, women were unaware of society, but the current situation shows entirely different images and they are aware that they are equally involved in all societal activities.

Legal Empowerment:

Legal empowerment refers to the legal protection that women require in order to protect themselves from cultural restrictions, harassment, superstitions and health issues. Educate women about their civil rights, exercise their legal rights, prepare and distribute publications about women’s legal freedom, offer quality literary programs about legal empowerment etc.

SOCIAL MEDIA AND EMPOWERMENT:

One of the proposed strategies to enhance the performance and engagement of entrepreneurs, as well as to foster economic development, is the utilization of social media by women (Alhakimi & Albashiri, 2023; Ajjan et al., 2014). It is believed that the engagement of female entrepreneurs in emerging markets with social media will enhance their self-efficacy and social capital, thereby providing them with a sense of empowerment. The internet has become indispensable for businesses, leading to greater success in entrepreneurship. Through various online media platforms, such as blogs, banner advertisements, websites, and notably social media channels, consumers have begun to engage with businesses (Batool et al., 2022). The advent of information technology has revolutionized all sectors of work, particularly in the expansion of business marketing services due to recent advancements. A few years ago, internet networks evolved into a global communication hub through sharing and tracking.

As noted by Andriole (2010) organizations have experienced considerable effects from the influence of social media in connecting with women and users. They utilize social media to access individuals' networks to gain insights into their preferences and opinions for improving profitability. Establishing social media accounts on platforms such as Facebook, LinkedIn, or Twitter has become a common practice for engaging with customers (Hassan et al., 2023). A variety of social media technologies and platforms are available to empower women and others to disseminate information more effectively. This contemporary form of social media, which allows users to communicate through text, images, audio, video, and data, is increasingly popular among internet users. The application of social media for communication goes beyond typical internet users. Women have the autonomy to disclose as much or as little personal information as they wish on platforms like Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn. This has resulted in a substantial volume of data that can be readily shared, searched, advertised, enhanced, and generated. Social media also aids in connecting users to social networks where they can interact and engage concurrently (Alhakimi & Albashiri, 2023). Furthermore, platforms like Facebook have created a unique connection between individuals and information, providing significant opportunities for advertising and information exchange. Additionally, various other social media platforms, including blogs, have established networking environments where women can share comments and ideas on events to enhance their visibility and outreach.

These platforms act as essential tools for attracting customers and tracking the popularity and reputation of products. The benefits of utilizing social media encompass time efficiency, targeting specific audiences, fostering relationships, and being cost-effective (Batool et al., 2022; Kirtis & Karahan, 2011). In comparison to other widely used public media, such as television, social media holds a distinct advantage. Unlike traditional media, which experiences a significant delay between broadcasting and real events, social media offers real-time updates. Furthermore, numerous social networking platforms are available at no cost. This renders social

media a financially viable option for businesses seeking to promote themselves. Women can attract followers, subscribe to newsletters, and engage with various social media platforms. A diverse array of social media options exists, including content-sharing platforms like YouTube and Flickr, as well as social networks such as LinkedIn and Facebook (Batool et al., 2022). The increasing prevalence of social media signifies its emergence as a crucial tool for businesses of all sizes. It plays a vital role in the lives of women and significantly impacts their decision-making processes. Social media can facilitate the promotion of campaigns and initiatives designed to empower women. It has enabled women to recognize their worth, cultivate confidence, pursue their passions, and draw inspiration from successful figures within their fields of interest. Now a day's Social media is evolving as a change agent.

The manner that information is sent and received globally is being altered by it. Every day, its use is growing at a rapid pace worldwide.

Social media features that support women's empowerment:

1. The existence of groups for women.
2. The presence of female support networks.
3. The availability of pertinent data and data unique to women.
4. Leadership with a feminist bent.
5. Social networking.
6. Understanding of a favourable policy environment.

The advantages of social media:

Social media offers a number of advantages, such as the following:

User Visibility: Social media platforms facilitate simple communication and content or idea sharing. People are interconnected in ways that go much beyond geographic borders. Social media's increasing popularity has led to a rise in knowledge, made information sharing and transfer easier, and enabled women to publish inspirational ideas and share information with others. Women now use social media on a daily basis, making their private lives visible to the world. (2011, Satpathi)

Building an Audience: Creating an audience for one's work is one of the many advantages of social media for artists and entrepreneurs. Because anyone may publish their business and do commerce online, social media has sometimes removed the requirement for a distributor. When a performer shares a song on Facebook, for example, their friends immediately see it and share it with their own networks.

Active interaction with your audience: Social media distinguishes itself as a distinctive marketing strategy that enables a direct connection with your intended audience. When people opt to follow your social media account, you can identify those who have an interest in your brand. This platform aids your business in multiple ways, including enhancing your understanding of customer preferences, providing outstanding customer support, and collecting valuable information about your audience.

Establish your brand: A key benefit of social media marketing is the opportunity to establish your brand. By engaging with potential leads, you present your brand to them. The chance to share organic content at no cost enables you to continually enhance brand recognition among your audience.

Increase website traffic: Using social media to promote your company's website can be a very successful tactic. Numerous social networking sites allow you to post content along with a link to your website. Your audience is more likely to click on the link if you create engaging content. They can therefore visit your website to find out more about your company.

Disadvantages of social media:

In any marketing strategy, there are inevitably drawbacks. These drawbacks do not indicate that the approach is ineffective, but rather, they represent potential obstacles that may need to be overcome during the campaign. The disadvantages of utilizing social media can be outlined as follows:

1. Absence of emotional bonding
2. Decline in face-to-face communication abilities
3. Portrayal of insincere emotions leading to a decrease in familial intimacy

4. Reduction in comprehension and empathy
5. Exposure to negative feedback.

Methodology

The aforementioned objectives indicate that this research is evaluative in nature. In order to achieve the study's goal, primary and secondary data were analysed in this essentially empirical investigation. Primary data was gathered via scheduled techniques, interviews, and observation. The secondary data was collected from a variety of published sources, including journals, bulletins, and reports from different government agencies, books, and magazines, multiple websites, textbooks, and other sources, which offered a solid theoretical framework for carrying out this research

Sampling

Considering the time limitations and the characteristics of the respondents, a sampling strategy has been implemented for the research. A total of 100 respondents from the study area were chosen utilizing a purposive sampling method to facilitate a more comprehensive analysis.

Analysis

Table: 1. Impact of Social Media on empowerment of rural women

The objective of the present study was to gain a deeper understanding of the effects of social media on empowerment of rural women. A sample consisting of 100 respondents was utilized. To achieve this, the subsequent results were derived from the data after it was analysed using the appropriate statistical techniques

S.N.	Impact of social media	No. of respondents	Percentage
1.	Increased information and lesson's on health and hygiene	07	07%
2.	Enhanced relation and intimacy building	12	12%
3.	Emotional support	10	10%
4.	Getting new information and opportunities	20	20%
5.	Increased self-esteem and confidence	09	09%
6.	Getting opportunities for self-decision making	13	13%
7.	Increased connectivity	11	11%
8.	Political consciousness	06	06%
9.	Awareness about legal protection	04	04%
10.	Increased digital financial inclusion	08	08%

The above table demonstrates that 07 respondents (07%) out of 100 enhanced understanding of reproductive health, hygiene and nutrition via info graphics and brief videos. 12 respondents (12%) out of 100 Enhanced relation and intimacy building because connection improved socio-metric skills and make them intimate and belongingness. Sharing personal narratives, images and videos on social media fostered a feeling of intimacy and connected with each other. 10 respondents (10%) out of 100 social media gave respondents a secure place to express their emotions, ideas and experiences while getting emotional support and affirmation from online groups. 20 respondents (20%) out of 100 were getting new information and opportunities because social media helped them to real time monitoring of market prices for agricultural products and awareness of government welfare programs. Besides this it served new probability of getting job, work or employment related news. 09 respondents (09%) out of 100 increased their self-esteem and confidence because their individual voices are validated and they feel a sense of belonging when they participate in online groups. Other than this enhancements in self-assurance, autonomous reasoning and the capacity to question conventional gender roles within the home. 13 respondents (13%) out of 100 Getting opportunities for self-decision making because by granting access to information, financial resources and international networks established a route from passive involvement to proactive, autonomous decision making. 11 respondents (11%) out of 100 increased connectivity to each other because social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram and WhatsApp have facilitated maintaining connections with family, friends and acquaintances, irrespective of geographical separation. 06 respondents (06%) out of 100 accessed to information regarding voting rights, local governance (Gram Panchayats) and updates on national policies that were once filtered through male family members. 04 respondents (04%) out of 100 increased understanding about legal protection through social media like civil rights

and legal safeguards against harassment or disputes related to land rights. 08 respondents (08%) out of 100 increased digital financial inclusion because interaction with digital content frequently served as an entry point to mobile banking, digital payment systems and information regarding micro-loans and government subsidies.

As a result, the largest segments of the respondents (20%) were getting new information and opportunities. They said that social media empowered them to establish their own enterprises, including handicrafts, textiles and food processing. Moreover, they have facilitated access to financial services, such as banking and insurance. Respondents reported that social media was extremely beneficial while staying at home during Covid-19, as it was an accurate way to obtain information during this time.

Future Prospects and their Policy Implications

1. Social media platforms can assist rural women in acquiring digital literacy skills, thereby improving their capacity to navigate the digital landscape.
2. Governments have the opportunity to invest in digital infrastructure such as internet connectivity and mobile networks to enhance social media access in rural regions more and more.
3. Governments should establish policies aimed at ensuring the online safety and security of rural women, addressing issues related to cyber bullying and harassment.
4. It is essential for governments and organizations to create digital literacy programs specifically designed for the needs of rural women, thereby improving their proficiency in using social media effectively.
5. Encourage the formation of partnerships among governments, organizations and social media platforms to advance the empowerment of rural women.
6. Initiate social media campaigns aimed at promoting the empowerment of rural women and tackling social challenges.

Conclusion

"To inspire the populace, it is essential to awaken women. When she takes action, the village progresses, the village advances, and the nation evolves." - Pandit Jawahar Lal Nehru. Nevertheless, significant gaps persist, and the realities faced by women are in constant flux, with new forms of discrimination arising regularly. The research outlines the goals and evaluates the status of women on social media, as well as its influence on various aspects of women's empowerment, equity, and dignity. A crucial factor for effective action is the degree to which the multiple roles of women have been acknowledged and how these roles contribute to alleviating their burdens. For the successful empowerment of women, it is imperative to embrace their affinity for technology and cultivate valuable lifelong skills; this will enhance their chances of achieving success in life. In stark contrast, many women, even in developing nations, still lack access to these information technologies due to economic and political barriers such as inadequate infrastructure, financial constraints, and oppression. The social media platform was primarily established as a tool for informing rural women and has proven to be an effective means of mobilization for their empowerment. Although social media has had a significantly positive effect on women's empowerment, issues such as fraud, cybercrimes, and other online offenses pose serious threats to its usage. Additionally, challenges including concerns about privacy and security, mental health issues like anxiety and depression, and the risk of addiction are intrinsic to the use of social media platforms. The aforementioned results indicate that the utilization of social media by rural women has a beneficial effect on empowering women in rural areas.

Social media has undeniably become a transformative instrument for women's empowerment in India, altering the dynamics of gender equality and offering women unparalleled opportunities for self-expression, advocacy, and socio-economic progress. By allowing women to elevate their voices, confront traditional gender norms, and foster solidarity through online communities, platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and LinkedIn have evolved into influential channels for empowerment. Movements like #MeToo, #IWillGoOut, and #PinjraTod have illustrated how digital activism can contest patriarchal systems, shape public discourse, and promote social change. Additionally, social media has created avenues for women entrepreneurs and small business proprietors, enabling them to establish digital marketplaces and network professionally without depending on conventional, male-dominated marketing avenues. Through initiatives such as the Digital India campaign, rural women are progressively gaining access to the digital realm, enhancing their capacity to engage in the economy and elevate their socio-economic status. Furthermore, the increasing legal awareness nurtured by social media platforms has empowered women with the knowledge and confidence to assert their rights and pursue justice, thus empowering them both personally and politically. Nevertheless, the path toward fully harnessing the potential of social media for women's empowerment remains laden with obstacles. Online harassment, trolling, cyber bullying, and

the non-consensual dissemination of private images create a perilous digital environment for many women, constraining their engagement.

The gendered digital divide continues to pose a considerable obstacle, especially in rural regions, where patriarchal values and restricted access to technology persistently limit women's engagement with social media. The lack of representation of women among internet users in India, particularly in rural areas, highlights the urgent need for focused initiatives that enhance digital literacy and provide affordable internet access for all women. Tackling these issues necessitates collaborative efforts from all parties involved, including government entities, civil society organizations, technology firms, and the women themselves. More stringent enforcement of cyber regulations, comprehensive digital safety protocols, and the advancement of gender-sensitive algorithms and content moderation practices will contribute to establishing a safer and more inclusive digital environment for women.

Initiatives aimed at closing the digital divide through infrastructure enhancement, educational programs, and policy reforms will ensure that women from marginalized communities can also take advantage of the opportunities offered by social media.

The empowerment of women is a fundamental human right to which they are entitled. Social media serves as a tool for them to confront the new challenges presented in today's world. The promotion of these social media platforms should be encouraged to ensure that women's rights can be advocated to the fullest extent. By enhancing women's access to these platforms and websites, it would guarantee that all opportunities are accessible to everyone. Therefore, despite the criticism that social media often faces it can be argued that a regulated media will ultimately prove to be more beneficial than harmful in the long term. In rural areas, the status of women is in a deteriorated condition. Male members are prioritized, and girls are viewed as liabilities. A key factor in improving the status of women is the need for family members to change their perspectives and view girls as assets. They should provide equal opportunities for them and allow their participation in various tasks and activities that would elevate their status. Measures have been formulated to enhance the status of women. These initiatives are aimed at fostering educational attainment, enhancing opportunities for skill development, promoting access to employment, ensuring equal opportunities, eradicating criminal and violent behaviors, abolishing discriminatory practices, advancing effective communication skills, facilitating mobility, instilling moral and ethical values, and improving the status of widows. Social media plays a crucial role in transforming the social and cultural behaviors of women in rural areas. The impact of these changes is evident in their clothing, dietary preferences, communication styles, debates, and overall lifestyle. Additionally, it empowers them by raising awareness about critical issues and developmental activities. The social media also serves to educate rural populations on health and hygiene, agricultural practices, and environmental concerns. Social media has been recognized as a vital instrument for spreading information and fostering rural development. All things considered, social media is a potent instrument for empowering rural women by giving them access to knowledge, chances and relationships they can enhance their quality of life.

‘Think equal, build smart, and innovate for change’

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